

DESCRIPTION OF THE CHARACTER OF THE HERO AND PERSONAGES

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Abstract. *The role of fiction in our social society is incomparable. A work of art is considered the main factor in the formation and enrichment of the human spiritual world. Especially in today's storytelling, the new outlook of a person, the colors of the world of thought are reflected. This article describes the stylistic peculiarities of the oeuvre of Shukur Kholmiraev, who made a significant contribution to the Uzbek school of storytelling, through the description of the character of the hero and personages in writer's novel "Olabuji", discusses his role in Uzbek prose.*

Keywords: *artistry, writer's skill, role of word art, romantic painting, character of the hero, character of the personages, portrait image, writer's character creation skill, hero's mental world, image of a "living person".*

Getting into the reader's heart and keeping an important place in his memory requires the writer to describe the events he wants to describe in an impressive way. Because the more believable and lively are the events, heroes and characters that the reader is familiar with, the more the writer's ideas in the work affect him.

Portraiture is one of the tools that make heroes and characters come to life. "Like other image tools, a portrait has a place and function in a work of art. The place assigned to the portrait, the assigned task must be subordinated to a logic, a certain artistic law. A portrait cannot deviate from the ideological direction of the work" (Sultonova M.1969, 4, 14). No matter what type of portrait the writer uses, if he tries to reveal the spiritual world of the hero, to reflect his unique features, a living person will appear before the eyes of the reader.

So, the literary portrait serves not only to describe the outward and appearance of the heroes of the work, but also to reveal the spiritual world of the hero and to show their unique characteristics.

Each writer has his own, unique characteristics when creating a portrait. As an example, let's take a look at the skill of creating portraits of Abdulla Kadiri and Abdulla Qahhor, whom the people's writer of Uzbekistan Shukur Kholmiraev learned directly from.

Shukur Kholmiraev has a unique role in raising the traditions of Abdulla Qadiri and Abdulla Qahhor to a new level in storytelling. For example, Sh. Kholmiraev developed the traditions of Abdulla Qadiri's depiction of nature in Uzbek storytelling. The wild naturalness and mystery of nature in the story "Feast of the Demons", the beauty of this naturalness and mystery to the extent that it frightens the human heart, has risen to a new level in Shukur Kholmiraev's novel "Olabuji".

It will not be an exaggeration to say that Sh. Kholmiraev continued the traditions of A. Kadyri in matters of creating the color (spirit) of time and space in artistic language, the manifestation of character through springs in the spiritual world, the simplicity and conventionality of heroes who do not fit into the "shaped" rules, the ability to have a bold critical

attitude towards society, and is considered to be advanced among writers who have risen in the new conditions.

Rejection of the order or standard of living that the society, situation or circumstances impose on him, or at least, to inform himself of the displeasure of the second "I" in his body, are the leading features of the writer's characters. Excluding some works of Cholpon and Abdulla Qahhor, Uzbek storytelling and prose were dominated by propaganda for a long time. From the 60s, artistic analysis gradually took its place.

In this process, the characters of Sh. Kholmirzayev strengthened the spirit of the heroes in Uzbek prose, especially the lack of self-satisfaction and the desire for deeper self-realization. In this sense, the main goal of the writer is not to describe the actions of his characters in social life, but their intelligence. According to the author's understanding, intelligence is the axis of the hero. For this reason, the writer is interested not in the actions performed by the hero, the result of the event taken as a basis, but rather in the opening processes of the hero's intelligence in relation to this event and the result. In such cases, some of Sh. Kholmirzaev's stories, short stories, novels, dramatic works, and the character of the heroes in them leave the impression that the reader or critic, sometimes even the author of the work, has a controversial attitude that has not been clearly resolved. In particular, this can be said about the novel "Olabuji". Endless hesitations in the heart of Ulton, the main character of the work - self-examination, instability in the inner world, his reaction to the past and present, events happening in himself and the environment, the process of his mental suffering - these are the hero's attempts to understand himself.

The novel "Olabuji" is one of the last novels created in Uzbek literature before the independence of Uzbekistan. It was written in 1991, and in 1992 it was referred to the readers' verdict in the "Sharq yulduzi" magazine. This novel is called by the writer as a story bigger than a literary novel. When he was asked why he called the work that way, he said, "Olabuji" was published in "Sharq yulduzi" magazine last year. I defined the genre of this work as a bigger story rather than a novel. I did this to fool myself. When I call a novel, it seems that the events branch and scatter. If I call a story, then I can restrain myself. Anyway, even so, it took 400-500 pages" [5, 124].

In this novel, Shukur Kholmirzaev highlighted life events and conflicts and expressed his reaction to them. He put bigger and bigger problems in the scenes of small life pictures. He finds the most subtle aspects of events and situations selected from life, finds characteristic points, describes them in detail, and through this makes a deep artistic analysis of the relationship between man and society. Fully describes a person, the experiences of the heroes, the conflicts between them, and spiritual values. As the first factor that ensures the artistry of the work, the author writes about the materials that interest him and are well known to him.

The artist created his own independent artistic perception of the spirit of the time through the events that he took as the object of the image.

In the work, he put forward ideas like both internal and external collapse of the existing socio-political system, the occupation of Uzbekistan by Russia, like other fraternal republics, as a result its living in the style of a dependent and colonial country of Russia, the emergence of a new type of leaders due to the excessive size of farms, and becoming of these leaders as a terrible symbol of the crisis of totalitarian regime, seeking people's interest by the social "Unity Movement" at the starting points, giving the status of the State Language to Uzbek language, the struggle for independence, the movement of national awakening, the settlement of spiritual

meanness under the banner of women's liberation, "The National Liberation Movement as a natural process" [6, 1]. These ideas are embedded in the psychology, fate, and events of the people depicted in the work. It is so ingrained that even without the author hinting at these ideas, we come to the author's own conclusion.

The work was able to openly show us the horrors of yesterday: the spiritual and moral decline of people, ecological decay, and the apathy and indifference of our people. Importantly, we can say that the work describes the spiritual decline in the minds of people.

The events of the work take place in one of the villages of Olatog district of Surkhandarya. Heroes are ordinary people that can come across in our lives.

Shukur Kholmiraev tries to find answers to the questions that are always bothering us through the interpretation and analysis of the heroes of the novel Toqliboy Kochgarov, Ulton Sultanov, Bahar, Botaboy Sopi, Tarakanov, Makhfirat Egamkulova, Dunyo, Sultan bobo and a number of such characters. In this, he examines the character and mentality of our contemporaries whom we lived and are still living with.

In the novel, we encounter various destinies and events that occur in various aspects of our lives. As a result, as an ordinary person, we feel like a participant in the story. All the people participating in the novel - Ulton, Bahar, Toqliboy Kochgarov, Botaboy Sopi, Sultan bobo, Makhfirat Egamkulova, Dunyo, Ashim, Hurrām, Nabi - are embodied as living people before our eyes. Through these images, the fate of our national heroes like Tangriberdi dodkho will not fail to make us suffer.

In the process of creative mastering of the world each writer gains the experience, his own way of seeing, perceiving, understanding and explaining the world. When thinking about the writer's skill, style and visual art, there is a need to act based on these elements.

One of the main characters of the novel is Ulton Sultanov, a simple village teacher and prominent writer. The writer described the life of this hero full of suffering in such a way that it is natural for the reader to feel pity for Ulton, hatred for the society that killed the young man and turned him into "Olabuji", and the leaders who play a major role in this society.

Some writers, in order to prove the change in the character of heroes and personages, describe it by reflecting their relationship to the events in the midst of extraordinarily acute events taking place in society, while some writers can prove the change in the character of heroes and personages through a single detail" [12, 14]. In fact, every artist uses details in his work. This detail connects all events in the work and serves to reveal the author's idea. "An interesting detail, a beautiful fragment increases the value of the work that it serves to promote the idea with this interestingness and beauty" [4, 123], says the writer Abdulla Kahhor. The writer used the detail of the bear to reveal the spirit of Ulton, the main idea of the work.

The work begins with Ulton reading the story "Brown Bear" by Seton Thompson. He becomes so interested in this story that even the call of his teacher cannot make him lose his thoughts about the bear", Ulton's thoughts the brown bear's going unwittingly to a cave in search of his own death, falling asleep after being fed up with the strange smell coming out of the cave, so some animals' knowing the place of their death without realizing it, and man's... inability to do so, also clarify our thoughts.

While reading the work, the reader begins to see bear-like qualities in Ulton, too. "When Ulton went to the girl's side, somehow crouched down, so to speak... he looked like a bear, yes, some fluffy-aggressive creature.

In order to make his opinion clearer, the writer includes a story [10, 148] from his grandmother (An old woman Tiniqoy – the claim is ours - M.H.) about a girl stolen by a bear when she was young. In the work, he describes this story in the way he heard it in the shepherds' talk [8, 37]. So, the writer continues his thoughts with the following philosophical thoughts:

“There are moments in a person's life when he himself does not know what he is thinking, but the actions appear as if they were the result of a deep thought. Therefore, it should be noted at this point that writers sometimes have no choice but to describe only the behavior of the hero, if the means of explaining the thoughts of the characters explain their actions: but they are sure of this fact that an impartial person does not look at these actions with suspicion at all.

Man is a complex creature, and the people of pen are just one of these people” [8, 86].

In the novel, the last moments of the totalitarian system are described in the style of time, that is, in the form of a unit of time in which the characters act. Because the period experienced many historical events, it allows to create impressive and full-fledged characters. As we get to know Ulton and the other characters, we become convinced of this. Especially, the tragedy of Ulton, whose fate ended like the fate of a creature called "Olabuji", does not stop us from excitement, and our hatred for the evil system that made it like this increases. "Literature... is the literature because convinces us that a fifteen-year-old boy can be the captain of a whole ship and take it out of the clutches of death" [7, 76] wrote Sh. Kholmiraev in one of his articles. In the process of reading this novel, we also agree with this opinion. After all, the writer was able to convince us of the events in the work with his skills.

Bahar is one of the characters who completes the character of Ulton in the work. At first, the reader meets Bahar in the office of Toqliboy Kochkarov in the following way: "She was wearing a white shirt and a striped skirt, her jet-black hair was cut short and fell to her shoulders, and her eyes were bright... She was the head doctor of the outpatient clinic in Oksuv." [9, 31].

To protect the girls like Bahar from entering into dead ends under the influence of people like Toqliboy Kochgarov and Makhfirat Egamkulova, to preserve the feelings of virginity, modesty, and nobility in their nature, and to return women to their ancient spiritual purity are of the main ideas of the work. Only then, the Bahar's tragedy will not be the tragedy of any other contemporary, our friend. The image of Bahar in the novel has a great educational value from this point of view.

As the writer himself said, the characters of each of his works, be they positive or negative, try to approach him as much as possible in a positive and negative way. After all, our people say that "God himself is blameless". Therefore, every person has good and bad qualities. We cannot admit this on our own. Many writers ignore this and try to portray positive characters with positive traits and negative characters with negative traits. This has a negative effect on the value of the work. We notice that Shukur Kholmiraev paid great attention to this situation in his works. In particular, the above-mentioned leaders in the novel "Olabuji" are also observed.

"The task of the novel is not to raise issues, but to absorb the issues that come across in life into the human destiny", to show the dramas hidden under these issues, and to show them through artistically perfect images. And this, in turn, depends on everything in a work of art, including the importance of the raised issue, the perfection of the artistic image, that is, the ability of the writer to create a "living person" capable of shaking the reader" [2, 116-117]. The ability to create a "living person" in turn depends on how well one can use psychological analysis, how well he or she can integrate it into the texture and problem of the work. [11, 56].

The writer was able to create such "living people" in the work. As we mentioned above, the characters of Ulton and Toqliboy Kochkharov are at the heart of the novel.

In general, the novel depicts life in one of the remote mountain villages in Surkhandarya and in the center of the district.

In this work, Sh. Kholmiraev made good use of the classic features of the novel genre and further enriched its possibilities due to the freedom, objectivity, and breadth of the image. The open, sometimes impartial and neutral attitude of the writer to sharp debates, sharp internal dialogues in the psyche, and the actions of the hero created new opportunities for revealing the essence of the images.

It is as if the author gave a symbolic meaning to the name of the novel: "Olabuji". Maybe it's the Shura regime, maybe it's Ulton, who was declared insane while being still healthy. Wasn't that a grumbling giant bear that appeared on the orphan peak? Isn't this bear Ulton, or has Ulton's spirit moved to him? May be Olabuji is Adalat or Erkdr in the same spirit? It is up to the reader to come to a conclusion [1, 509].

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